

Architectural Scalability of Neural Network Inference Using Task-based Programming

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Abstract

The internal structure of interactions in a hidden network can be inferred using a maximum likelihood estimate based on a record of its external behavior, within the framework of the kinetic Ising model. Beyond its origins in statistical physics, solutions to this problem can model the internal structure of a hidden neural network based on activity recordings from a laboratory setting, or the training process of an artificial neural network in the context of machine learning. The primary obstacle to its practical application is that the amount of computational work required grows rapidly with the dimensions of the represented network, but the vast majority of the operations can be independently evaluated in parallel. In this paper, we investigate the performance characteristics of a proxy application that models this growth, with the purpose of examining its suitability as a candidate application for future exascale platforms. While the application implies an abundant amount of parallelizable computation, the practical scalability of a particular implementation depends on the distribution of its underlying data structure in memory, and the resulting interactions with the memory system of the target architecture. We investigate three different programming strategies that cover different trade-offs in terms of memory access, from a process-based implementation that partitions the global workload into parallel parts that are strictly sequenced internally, through a combination of thread parallelism and statically scheduled iterations, to a task-based implementation that exposes all the work in terms of potentially parallel work units and schedules their sequencing at run-time. We find that this trade-off leads to implementations that can utilize computing platforms of growing size comparably well, displaying near-linear speedup on our test system, which makes the application a promising candidate for extreme scale computations. For the present test systems, however, scheduling the computation at run-time comes with an overhead that is not amortized by the gains from additional scheduling flexibility, suggesting that the process-based implementation provides the most favorable scalability on present architectures.

1. Introduction

The kinetic Ising model from statistical physics presents a highly parallel method to analyze non-equilibrium systems, which is applicable to the problem of estimating the internal structure of hidden neural networks, based on limited experimental data records of its external behavior [1]. Estimating hidden structures of neural networks is a challenging problem in neural computational research, as the experimental data that can be obtained from *e.g.* neural recordings of living tissue only provide a limited view of network structure, and inferring the most likely structure of the remaining network by an expectation-maximization method requires substantial amounts of computation. The utility of such methods is related to the size of network that can be represented and the time required to infer its structure, both of which invite highly parallel solutions. Previous studies[2][3] have shown that successive generations of accelerator hardware provide improved performance with the evolution of their memory subsystems, but they have so far been inconclusive with respect to consistently providing better absolute performance than shared memory parallelizations on conventional architectures. This suggests that performance is linked to non-trivial interactions with the memory hierarchy.

Task-based programming models aim to exploit the potential for hiding memory latency by exposing a far greater number of independent, parallel tasks than the number of physical processing cores, thus trading the performance overhead of creating an execution schedule for the possible savings of dynamically adapting it to run-time conditions.

This paper investigates the effectiveness of a task-based approach by comparing three different implementations of a proxy application that represents the performance characteristics of the problem. The first relies exclusively on MPI processes, the second combines MPI processes at the compute node level with OpenMP

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Fig. 1: (a) Network representation; (b) Network extruded along the time axis

worksharing constructs within each compute node, and the final one replaces the worksharing constructs with OpenMP tasks. They cover a spectrum of possibilities from rigidly synchronized iterations to run-time scheduling of independent work units, in order to compare the effectiveness of the latter with conventional programming techniques.

We find that all three implementations can exploit the great amount of parallelizable work inherent in the computation, displaying nearly linear performance improvements in strong scaling experiments up to 1152 cores. In terms of absolute performance, we find that the MPI-only implementation executes substantially faster than the hybrid alternatives, suggesting that the benefits of the application’s regular memory access pattern outweigh the advantages of flexible work unit scheduling.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2. describes the origin of the proxy application, and motivation for studying its performance. Section 3. describes the computation it carries out, and its initial design. Section 4. describes the adaptations we apply in order to separate parallel tasks from the dimensions of the executing platform. Section 5. presents our experimental results from comparing the range of implementations, and discusses their implications for scalable implementation strategies. Section 6. concludes the study, and identifies directions for future research.

2. Background and Motivation

HPC applications inherently require interdisciplinary collaborations, with application experts providing the knowledge of the application domain, and HPC experts providing knowledge of large scale computing platforms. Performance representative proxy applications are research vessels to support such collaborations, and address the challenges associated with adapting full-scale application programs to novel programming models and architectures. By implementing particular solutions of a simplified problem instance, their intention is to remain short and simple to modify, yet capture the critical performance properties of a complete application, so that exploratory studies can be carried out prior to making expensive design decisions that determine the evolution of more elaborate solutions.

The proxy application in this study has been developed in collaboration with the Kavli Institute for Systems Neuroscience, specifically to model the computational requirements of inferring a hidden neural network from empirical recordings of its activity. Because the approach is fundamentally neutral to whether the network structure has a natural or artificial origin, however, its performance and scalability is also relevant with application to data science, which plays a strategic part in the objectives of the NoMAD European Centre of Excellence.

3. Model Problem and Proxy Application

The proxy application is motivated by numerical investigation into the reconstruction of hidden couplings in a nonequilibrium Ising model[1]. The goal of this computation is to consider an external record of behavior from a network which combines visible and hidden nodes, and infer its internal structure by estimating the hidden couplings with maximum likelihood. Fig. 1 (a) shows the representation of the network as K layered, weighted adjacency matrices, parameterized in the total number N of nodes per layer, and the number M of visible nodes, which implies the number P of hidden nodes. Interconnections can be categorized in terms of

$P \times P$ hidden/hidden interactions, $M \times M$ visible/visible interactions, and $P \times M + M \times P$ hidden/visible interactions, with the corresponding submatrices shown in differing shades of grey.

Inference proceeds by combining this structure with a time series of T external observations, which produces the central data structure of the application. This is shown in Fig. 1 (b), where the K dimension has been collapsed for clarity. The network structure combines with a number of observations that is several orders of magnitude greater than the K, N, M dimensions, and the inference maintains several variables for each, which become multidimensional arrays of sizes $K \times P \times P \times T$, $K \times M \times M \times T$, $K \times P \times M \times T$, *etc.*, depending on which submatrix the variable pertains to.

The extreme length of the T axis relative to K, N , and M , creates a large memory requirement. The operations on these arrays, however, mainly consist of a large number of element-wise combinations, offset from each other by at most $K+1$ positions. This suggests that the computation implicitly contains abundant parallelism, and previous experiments[2][3] have leveraged highly parallel accelerator units to exploit this, seeking to identify suitable compute node architecture for increased scale.

Execution proceeds in two repeated stages: a computationally intensive inner loop which proceeds to convergence each iteration, interspersed by a series of reductions of global state before the next iteration. Because the convergence criterion can require long-running computations, our proxy application differs from a full implementation in two main aspects. Firstly, it is parametric in the number of inner loop iterations, and therefore does not produce an accurate result. Secondly, its input data are artificially, rather than experimentally generated; a random network is generated at initialization, its external behavior is derived, the hidden connections are slightly perturbed, and the computation aims to verify that the system converges back to the generated, known configuration. While this procedure is insufficient to produce novel insights about measured activity from actual neural networks, we argue that it emulates the performance characteristics of the computation, and therefore functions as a vessel for realistic experiments with approaches to parallelization that can be elaborated upon in the actual application context.

The element-wise combinations of array variables that make the application amenable to extreme scale parallelization take the form of a series of nested loops that depend on the dimensions of the combined variables. The majority of the operations amount to aggregations of dot products, with the exception of one exponentiation and five hyperbolic tangents. While this admits implementation in terms of calls to highly optimized L1 BLAS operations, preliminary experiments suggested that the resulting number of calls to operations of low arithmetic intensity make it favorable to explicitly specify them as nested loop constructs in the source code, and thus expose them for compiler optimizations.

As an illustration of the type of structure that recurs throughout the program, a sequential implementation that combines weights from the network structure with two $M \times T$ and $P \times T$ sized array variables to update a pair of $K \times P \times T$ and $K \times M \times T$ sized array variables is shown below:

```
for ( int_t t=0; t<T; t++ )
  for ( int_t k=0; k<K; k++ )
    for ( int_t y=0; y<P; y++ )
      for ( int_t x=0; x<M; x++ )
      {
        DJM(k,y,t) += JouI(k,y,x)*JouI(k,y,x) * OMM(x,t);
        DTTH(k,x,t) += Jout(k,x,y)*Jout(k,x,y) * DTH(y,t);
      }
}
```

The most important property of this pattern is that the innermost loop body consists entirely of operations that can be executed independently, and their number grows very rapidly with the input problem size, so each similar stage can be parallelized. The communication requirements of the application stems from the fact that some of these arrays require operands that are shifted by relative indexing differences of up to $K + 1$ steps along the T axis, as shown below:

```
for ( int_t t=0; t<T-k-1; t++ )
  for ( int_t y=0; y<M; y++ )
    Rhs(y,t) += Mu(y,t) * DTTH(k,y,t+k);
```

Each step is repeated in a large number of sequentially dependent iterations. Without this requirement, the application would be *embarrassingly parallel*[4]. The complete computation is dominated by a series of 29 similarly nested loop constructs, and our candidate implementations focus on different approaches to partitioning the outermost, T -sized loop between processing cores.

4. Implementation Strategies

As the application is known to exhibit irregular scalability properties with various memory hierarchies, our experiments focus on three different implementations: a pure MPI parallelization, a hybrid MPI+OpenMP parallelization that utilizes work-sharing constructs, and a hybrid MPI+OpenMP parallelization that utilizes task constructs.

Fig. 2: Distributed Memory Partitioning and Border Exchange

4.1. MPI Parallelization

Our MPI implementation works by partitioning the data structures for each variable using a 1D domain decomposition along the T axis. Fig. 2 illustrates the necessary border exchange operations this requires per iteration. All exchanges send and receive $K + 1$ sets of boundary values to neighboring processes in both directions. The inner loop requires frequent exchanges of 10 variables: 3 sets of M scalars, 3 sets of $K \times M$ arrays, 2 sets of P scalars, and 1 set of $K \times P$ arrays. The less frequent stages of the outer loop body requires the additional exchange of 2 sets of P scalars, and `MPI_Allreduce` operations of $3M + P + 1$ scalars. As this implementation only relies on MPI parallelism, all speedup stems from the partitioning of the problem's T dimension, and further nested loops are executed sequentially by each processing core.

The advantage of this implementation is that the memory access patterns created by sequential iterations of rectangular arrays are highly regular and predictable. Traversal of multidimensional arrays benefits from architectural features such as prefetching and branch prediction, and the program pattern is highly amenable to compiler optimizations such as loop unrolling and automatic vectorization. Its disadvantages are that it creates a measure of data duplication, and that MPI processes are suitable for coarse-grained parallel work units. The former manifests in the duplication of data that must be read-accessible to more than one process: near subdomain boundaries, values that are internal to one subdomain must be buffered, transmitted, and stored as an additional copy in the halo region of the neighboring subdomain. Within the shared memory of a compute node, the cost of this transmission and duplication is higher than necessary, as processing cores can directly access each others' data when programmed using the finer grained parallelism of multithreading.

4.2. MPI with OpenMP Worksharing Constructs

The MPI+Workshare implementation retains the MPI communication pattern for parallelization on distributed memory machines, but adds `#pragma omp parallel for` constructs to all T -indexed loops, so that thread-level parallelism can be utilized internally on shared memory compute nodes.

Its advantage is that this removes the memory duplication and communication calls associated with node-internal border exchanges, and provides the opportunity to dynamically adapt thread execution to the workload. The use of worksharing constructs makes this variant an intermediate case between the MPI and MPI+Task approaches, as it eliminates the need for explicit message passing at the shared memory level, but retains the regular memory access pattern and bulk-synchronous execution pattern.

The disadvantage is that the sequential dependency between parallelizable steps within each iteration requires threads to synchronize at the end of each thread-parallel stage, and as parts of the iteration space are assigned uniformly to each thread, the resulting sequence of memory fences takes no advantage of the opportunity to reassign work in the event that some threads finish their work units earlier than others.

4.3. MPI with OpenMP Tasks

The MPI+Task implementation replaces the thread-level parallelism of the MPI+Workshare implementation with OpenMP `taskloop` constructs. This creates a pool of worker threads that can accept tasks dynamically, while a single thread iterates through the outermost loop and creates a task pool from the independent iterations that can be assigned to threads as they finish previous work.

Fig. 3: (a) Speedup; (b) Wall time for $N=25, M=3, K=2$ configurations, logarithmic time scale

The advantage of this approach is that it creates a potential for the run-time system to hide memory latency by more flexible scheduling of the parallel work units, and threads that finish before a predetermined, static schedule can be assigned additional work units.

Its disadvantage is that this dynamic task scheduling creates an overhead, as management of the task pool requires additional data structures internal to the run-time system, and the precise assignment of tasks to threads requires continuous evaluation.

5. Experimental Results and Discussion

5.1. Methodology

Experiments were carried out on an SGI Altix ICE X system with dual 8-core Intel Xeon E5-2670 processors, and 32GB of memory per node. Its Mellanox Infiniband FDR interconnect is configured as an enhanced hypercube, and hierarchically structured in multiples of 18 nodes per rack unit, with four rack units per physical cabinet.

Each implementation was tested for 50 stages with 10 inner loop iterations each, to produce steady state performance. MPI tests were carried out assigning one MPI rank to each available physical core. Both hybrid MPI+OpenMP variants were tested assigning one MPI rank to each node, and utilizing the 16-way thread parallelism at the shared memory level.

Experiments were run in strong scaling mode with $T = 10^6$. Linearly increasing values of N , M and K lead to cubically increasing problem sizes, keeping the relative weights of the workload from various submatrices proportional. Results were collected from runs up to the size of one physical cabinet in the system, with a single 16-core node as performance baseline. Scaling proceeded in multiples of the 18-node rack units, producing timings from batches of five runs on successive core counts of 16, 288, 576, 864, and 1152. The results are shown in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 3 shows speedup and walltime figures from all three implementations, using the smallest problem size of $N = 25, M = 3, K = 2$. As above, speedup figures are relative to the 16 core case for each implementation, but while they *scale* similarly well in terms of effectively partitioning the computational load, walltime performance figures are strikingly different: note the logarithmic scale of the vertical axis in Fig. 3 (b).

Fig. 4 shows speedup and walltime figures from the pure MPI implementation, for three problem sizes from $N = 25, M = 3, K = 2$ through $N = 75, M = 9, K = 6$, as well as a linear graph for comparison. Walltime measurements are included to show the effect of increased problem sizes, as the speedup figures are relative to the 16-core performance for each problem, and thus unsuitable for comparisons between the problem sizes. Walltime measurements for the 16-core case are omitted because their relative size obscures the remaining results by requiring an extensive vertical range.

5.2. Discussion

The speedup curves in Fig. 3 (a) support the intuition that the high growth rate in the number of independent operations *vs.* problem size makes the application a viable candidate for extreme scale computations. Fig. 3 shows that even in a strong scaling scenario using our smallest problem size, parallel speedup remains close to linear for all three implementations, although both variants which exploit node-internal shared memory begin to exhibit diminishing returns at a core count of 1152. The MPI parallel version shows some fluctuations about the linear comparison curve, with slight superlinearity at 288 and 576 cores, and a drop at 864 which disappears again at 1152 cores.

Fig. 4: (a) MPI speedup; (b) MPI wall time (excluding single node performance)

The MPI version’s deviations from linear scaling can be attributed to its tight coupling to the details of the memory hierarchy: as the computation is constantly accessing densely packed, multidimensional arrays where indexing strides depend directly on the combination of problem dimensions and parallel partitioning, some variability can be expected at sizes that align particularly with cache line sizes, vector lengths, and similar architectural details of the underlying platform. This also accounts for the minor observations of superlinear speedup. As the strong scaling mode assigns smaller problem partitions to each process when their number rises, we can expect superlinear behavior at points where the size of each individual partition admit it to fit completely in smaller memory levels, closer to the processing core. This effect has no significance for a practical scenario where the program is extended to model an actual neural network, as increases in available parallel hardware would be better translated into weak scaling mode, favoring larger input sizes over faster solution.

Because the speedup curves only relate the parallel gains of each implementation to its own performance at the smallest scale, it is equally interesting to observe the absolute execution time figures in Fig. 3 (b). The figure reveals that while the candidate implementations succeed almost equally well in dividing the parallel work, the performance parameters of the underlying architecture have a significant effect on their effectiveness. Noting the logarithmic scale of the vertical axis, it is clear how the architectural features that complex, superscalar processing cores surpass the benefits of increased parallelism by orders of magnitude for this computation. The range of latency hiding potential *vs.* communication requirements covered by our candidate implementations is evident in the ordering of their performance: lock-step execution which is frequently synchronized by border exchanges is most effective, exposing the maximal amount of parallel work and scheduling it at run-time is the least effective, and intermediate combination of reduced border exchanges with static thread scheduling falls between these two extremes.

These observations and the outcomes of previous studies[2, 3] suggest a combined recommendation of architectural choices with the view towards leveraging future exascale platforms. The parallel nature of the computation makes it highly *scalable* either on architectures which rely on massive parallelism and latency hiding, or conventional architectures with lower numbers of complex units. However, for the present generation of systems, the performance characteristics of the computation make it unlikely that it would be well served by a massively parallel array of lightweight computational cores. The evolution of recent GPU accelerator generations has shown a tendency towards increased complexity both in computational core designs and memory hierarchies. Thus, in the context of future exascale platforms, we expect the significance of this architectural difference to diminish over time.

The results in Fig. 4 show the performance of the MPI implementation, subject to increasing problem sizes. The absolute time requirement grows substantially, and the communication volume of the border exchange operation increases in proportion to the K and N dimensions. The significance of the latter can be seen in Fig. 4 (a); as the experiments are carried out in strong scaling mode, Amdahl’s law predicts diminishing returns of parallelism, at a scale determined by the problem size. Given our application’s high ratio of computation to communication requirements, it utilizes increasing processor counts up to and beyond the system size available for these tests with only moderate drops in efficiency, but these are visibly connected to, and exacerbated by, increases in per-iteration communication volume. As a candidate for migration to exascale platforms, this suggests that its suitability is mainly governed by the parameters of the input problem. Increasing values of T generate more parallelizable work while retaining constant per-iteration communication between neighbors in a 1D topology. Fixed T and growing network sizes K, N shift the point of diminishing returns toward smaller systems.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we have examined performance and scalability effects of applying three different programming approaches to a neural network inference proxy application, to evaluate the applicability of task-based programming. In scalability terms, we have found that task parallelism is an equally viable alternative to fixed schedules of synchronized iterations, but the run-time overheads of thread management are presently too large to make task based programming performance competitive on our test system.

As the performance-representative proxy application exhibits very favorable scalability characteristics, a natural extension of this work is to expand it to a full implementation, and examine the network sizes of practically applicable problems, so as to evaluate it as a candidate application for future exascale computations.

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